

THICK NCF COMPOSITE LAMINATES: LOW VELOCITY IMPACT PERFORMANCE

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SUMMARY: Thick section carbon fibre composite laminates are intended to be used as wing skins on large civil and military aircraft with thicknesses up to and beyond 30mm. In this work thick carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminates are manufactured using the resin film infusion method with triaxial and uni-directional non-crimped fabrics (NCF). Laminates up to 12mm thick have been successfully manufactured and tested. In particular interest in this research is the effect of a transverse impact near a free edge. Three impact energies were used to test the laminates, and the damage evaluated using ultrasonic C-scan and post impact residual strength tests. It was found that edge impacted laminates suffered from extensive delamination whereas centrally impacted laminates fibre breakage. This meant that edge impacted plates had better tensile residual strength compared to a centrally impacted plate; the opposite was true with compressive residual strength.

KEYWORDS: low velocity impact, thick NCF laminates, drop weight impact testing, explicit finite element analysis, ultrasonic C-scan, residual strength

INTRODUCTION

Thick section carbon fibre composite laminates are intended to be used as wing skins on large civil and military aircraft with thicknesses up to and beyond 30mm. Composite laminated panels are particularly vulnerable to transverse impact as has been widely reported [1]. This kind of event can create sub-surface damage that is not only invisible to the naked eye but extensive and structurally significant. Typically, extensive delaminations lead to much reduced in plane compressive strength in the thin laminates studied in the literature. This leads to conservative design and non-optimised use of composite materials.

Most research so far into impact has been on thin laminates, typically no thicker than 2 or 3mm. Only a few recent papers were found that analysed or experimented on what might be considered a thick laminate [2 - 4].

Impact of thin fibre reinforced laminates has been extensively studied and reported, for example [1, 5]. Considerable effort has been aimed at modelling impact event on a composite laminate, using a variety of approaches: closed form solutions [6], 3D continuum solid Finite Element Models [2, 7], 4-node layered shell FEM [8] and stacked 8-node 3D shell FE [9]. Usually the lay-up is modelled either explicitly with a layer of elements for each ply, or by using a composite element that smears the ply properties across the thickness of the element sometimes with integration points at each ply interface.

Very little research has been found that looks specifically at the damage arising from an impact near a free edge, Green's research [7] perhaps being the most relevant. An edge impact on a wing skin is not unlikely as it presents a large target area and will have many access holes. There are many experimental investigations into the effects of impact. Of interest has been the lay-up sequence where it has been shown that reducing the relative ply orientation between adjacent plies reduces delamination [10], investigation of the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination [11] and techniques for measurement of laminate damage post impact [12] for example. Despite this, impact damage is a phenomenon that is not well understood for every case hence research is on going.

In this work thick carbon fibre reinforced (epoxy) plastic laminates are manufactured using the resin film infusion method with triaxial and uni-directional non-crimped fabrics (NCF). Laminates up to 12mm thick have been successfully manufactured and tested. In particular interest in this research is the effect of a transverse impact near a free edge. Such free edges are inevitable in the design of a modern aircraft wing skin and the effect of an impact near such a feature has not been studied in detail. Experimental and numerical investigations have been performed and the results presented and discussed in this paper.

In addition to the experimental study, a parallel simulation study has been undertaken looking at the impact of thick laminates [14, 15].

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Impact Testing

An impact machine specially designed for the impact of thick composites was used for the tests in this research. It guides a steel impactor onto the target specimen by way of a steel channel section with guides bolted to its sides. This provides a very low loss system for delivering the impactor.

The plate is placed on a thick steel plate with a 200 mm diameter hole, with another plate bolted down on top, similarly with a 200 mm hole, to hold the specimen in place. The impactor had a 19 mm diameter ball bearing as the tup and capacity to have additional mass to vary the impact energy whilst keeping the impact height and thus velocity constant. A Kistler 8704B5000 K-Shear voltage mode was used to measure live accelerations during impact, from which impact force was derived

Two pairs of infrared diodes were used to measure the impactor's impact and rebound velocity, where a thin 30 mm long aluminium tab near to the tup of the impactor breaks the infrared beam as it passes; the first pair act as a trigger for the data acquisition system, the second measures the time for the tab to pass. The instruNet iNet-100B system was used at a sampling rate of 83 kHz per channel.

Table 1 details the test configurations. Three plate thicknesses were tested with nominal thicknesses of 4, 8 and 12 mm. All plates were subjected to both central impacts and near edge impacts, in the manner illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Arrangement for plate to be impacted. Left: edge impact, right: central impact.

Table 1: Impactor mass, drop height and energy configurations

Impactor body mass (kg)	Additional mass (kg)	Total Impactor mass (kg)	Drop height (m)	Estimated impact velocity (ms^{-1})	Estimated impact energy (J)
2.47	0	2.47	4.3	9.2	104
4.67	0	4.67	4.3	9.2	197
4.67	3.7	8.37	4.3	9.2	353

Fig. 2 to Fig. 5 show the results. Fig. 2 shows that the actual measured impact energies are approximately 100 J, 200 J and 375 J. The level of absorbed energy shows a linear variation with impact energy, at 0.72 J/J, or at an average of 72% of impact energy absorbed by the plate, so that a bigger impact energy entails more energy, or damage, absorbed by the plate. Also, there does not seem to be any clear pattern distinguishing the edge impacts from the central impacts.

Fig. 3 shows a general trend that as the plate thickness increases the impactor force increases. As the thicker plate is stiffer, the energy from the impactor is not so readily dissipated by plate bending. So the force from the impactor is bigger as it damages the plate in a more localised fashion, and the damage mechanisms requiring greater force: fibre breakage. Larger impact energies create bigger impactor forces as would be expected, and the edge impacts have lower forces compared to the central impacts.

Fig. 4 confirms that the amount of energy absorbed by the plate increases with larger impact energies, but also that this amount is independent to the thickness of the plate, and whether the impact is near a free edge or central. Fig. 5 shows that the impact event duration decreases with lower impact energies, increasing thickness and edge impacts. The reason for this dependence on thickness and impact location is similar: where the plate is less stiff, i.e. thinner or impacted near a free edge, it will deflect more. Bigger deflection means a longer impact event duration.

Fig. 2: Amount of the impact energy absorbed by the plate for all impacts from 4.3 m

Fig. 3: Maximum impactor force for all impacts from 4.3 m

Fig. 4: Amount of energy absorbed by the plate in all impacts from 4.3 m

Fig. 5: Impact event duration for all impacts from 4.3 m

The impacted plates were subjected to various techniques to evaluate the damage. Firstly the plates were scanned using ultrasonic C-scan, then coupons were machined from each plate

with the damage central, and tested quasi-statically for determination of residual strength in compression and tension.

Residual Strength Measurement

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the failure strengths in each impact category. Where multiple specimens were tested scatter bars show extent of the highest and lowest values making up the mean. There were no 400 J impacts planned on the 4 mm thick laminates and no 100 J impacts planned on the 12 mm thick laminates. In the end it was not possible to fail in tension the 12 mm thick laminates subjected to 200 J impacts as those impacts had not damaged the plates enough to reduce their strength to below the maximum practical test load of approximately 300 kN for a 50 mm wide coupon.

Fig 6: Tensile strength results comparing edge and central impacted specimens

The way in which impact damage is initiated and propagated in a composite means that the scatter is potentially large. The cracks and delaminations do not necessarily grow linearly and in a controlled manner. In fact more common is an unstable crack growth so in some impacted plates there will be more damage than others because the threshold has been reached. It is the delaminations that will reduce the compressive strength, and the fibre cracks that will reduce the tensile strength.

Fig. 6 shows that in general the edge impacted plates have a larger residual tensile strength than the centrally impacted plates. This is due to how the plate deforms and responds during the impact, which in turn leads to a form of damage being prevalent. The edge impacted plate is less stiff in out-of-plane bending both in terms of the (dynamic) inertial stiffness and the mechanical or static stiffness. Thus the resulting larger deflection means bigger bending shear forces in the plate, these giving rise to the creation and propagation of delaminations. The peak impactor force will also be lower meaning fewer fibre breaks. What this kind of

damage pattern means is that with more delaminations and fewer fibre breaks, the edge impacted plate will have a higher residual tensile strength.

Fig. 7 shows the residual compressive strength of the impacted plates. Following the argument above, the edge impacted plates have bigger delaminations. As the test is of the stability/buckling type the thickness of the coupon is critical to determining its strength, or the load at which buckling occurs; Euler showed that it is in fact dependent on the thickness cubed. The delaminations do not reduce the thickness of the coupon, but they have the effect of dividing the coupon into multiple sublaminates. The more interfaces that have delaminations, and the greater the extent of those delaminations the bigger the reduction in the compressive strength is. The results back up this theory, as in almost every case the compressive strength is lower for the coupon with edge impact damage.

Fig. 7: Compression results comparing edge and centrally impacted coupons

NDT C-Scans

As would be expected, the delamination area increases for impacts with higher energy. Fig. 8 shows back face amplitude C-scans (in blank and white for clarity) of impacts onto 8 mm thick laminates of three energies. For the two lower impact energies the central and edge impacts were performed on the same plate to conserve material. For the 400 J impact two plates were used to ensure there was no interaction between the larger damage areas. The scans show that edge delaminations grow considerably with impact energy, whereas the central delamination grows, but less dramatically. At 100 J the edge impact delamination is not symmetrical in shape, as the delamination has only spread above the impact point along the edge. This delamination is relatively deep within the plate following examination of the

mid-plane time of flight plot. At 200 J the edge delamination area is symmetrical in shape, and appears bounded by the size of the specimen clamp. The delamination extends beyond the clamp along the free edge and enters the plate at 45°. When the delamination goes within the specimen support region the boundary changes direction to a vertical line in the 0° direction. At 400 J the edge delamination grew bigger still, although still apparently limited in extent by the specimen support.

Fig. 8: Delamination area in 8 mm thick laminates subjected to increasing impact energy level

Fig. 9: Delamination areas for all specimens impacted from 4.3 m with lines passing through the average area at each energy

Fig. 9 shows the full pattern of the delamination area against the impact energy, it shows the delaminated area from each impact where the full height of the impact machine was used. The area was measured from the C-scan results using the free UTHSCSA ImageTool program (developed at the University of Texas Health Science Centre at San Antonio, Texas and available from the Internet by anonymous FTP from ftp://maxrad6.uthscsa.edu). Lines have been added to the graph that go through the average area at each impact energy for each plate thickness/impact position combination. Central impacts give a smaller delamination area in every case compared to the equivalent edge impact. In addition the increase in delamination area for each plate thickness and impact position is clear as the impact energy increases.

CONCLUSIONS

A detailed experimental study into the edge and central impact of thick composite plates has been conducted. Three impact energies were used to test the laminates, and the damage evaluated using ultrasonic c-scan and post impact residual strength tests. It was found that edge impacted laminates suffered from extensive delamination whereas centrally impacted laminates fibre breakage. This meant that edge impacted plates had better tensile residual strength compared to a centrally impacted plate; the opposite was true with compressive residual strength.

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